

Evaluation of sexual disposition and hiv-risk factors among students of tertiary and secondary educational institutions in bayelsa state

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ABSTRACT

Sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) are caused by bacteria, viruses, parasites, or fungi transmitted through bodily fluids like semen, vaginal fluids, or blood. Many are asymptomatic initially, increasing the unintentional spread, but untreated cases can lead to serious issues like infertility, chronic pain, or cancer. High-risk sexual activities, among others, have been reported to be risk factors for HIV. The sexual activities that are considered “high risk” are reported to be either carried out on the internet or carried out physically. A descriptive cross-sectional design was used for the study. The research area for this study was four educational institutions in Bayelsa State. The sample size was determined by the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) formula, which gave 357. This study adopted both stratified and convenience sampling techniques. Pearson chi-square and t-tests were carried out with no significant difference with the aid of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. The majority of students indulge in sexual intercourse (74.5%) and smoking marijuana and drinking alcohol before having sex (54.7%). Other reported high-risk behaviours include surfing the internet for sexual films (77.6%) and being pressured for sex (74.5%). The study concludes that female students within the 20-29 age bracket in two secondary and two tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State reported a high level of sexual depression for contracting HIV.

Keywords : Sexual behaviour, HIV risk factors, STDs, students, Bayelsa State, substance use, high-risk activities, cross-sectional study.

Background

Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is one of the sexually transmitted diseases. Its importance lies in the fact that, unlike other related diseases, it has the propensity to modify the host immune system, thereby providing opportunities for other infections to thrive (Weiss, 1993).

According to 2009 data, Bayelsa State has the third-highest

HIV prevalence in Nigeria at 9.1%. High rates of multiple partners, increased incidence of young women having sex with older partners, and reduced rates of condom use were stated to be the primary contributing factors. Other factors included a lack of comprehensive HIV knowledge, limited use of prenatal care services, and low uptake of HIV testing and counselling (HTC) (Bayelsa State ERPS report, 2009).

High-risk sexual activities, among others, have been reported to be risk factors of HIV. The sexual activities that are considered “high risk” are reported to be either carried out on the internet or carried out physically (Boies, 2002; Shaughnessy, Byers, & Walsh, 2011). The ones carried out on the internet, according to Sandra and Krystelle (2014), Shaughnessy et al. (2011), can be non-arousal (educational and relationship sexually stimulating materials), solitary-

arousal (sexually explicit stimuli, e.g., pornography), or partnered-arousal (interactive, sexting on online videos). The author, Shaughnessy, and others in 2011 also revealed that the prevalence of socially sexually-related activities was directly related to the type of online sexual activities (OSA). He reported the order of prevalence to be online sexual, non- Online Sexual, and partnered arousal.

Methods

Research Design

A descriptive cross-sectional design was used for the study. This was chosen to take a “snapshot” of educational institutions in the environment of the study.

Area of the Study

Bayelsa State, located in south-south Nigeria, is bounded to the north by Delta State, to the east by Rivers State, and to the south and west by the Atlantic Ocean. The state capital is Yenagoa. The research area for this study was four educational institutions in Bayelsa state, namely Niger Delta University (the state-owned university in a semi-urban setting), Federal University Otuoke (a Federal University in a semi-urban setting), Belary Secondary School (a modern secondary school in the state capital), and Otuasega SS (a secondary school in a rural setting).

Population for the Study

The population for this study comprised students of public tertiary institutions (Niger Delta University and Federal University, Otuoke) and Secondary schools (Otuasega and Den Biliary Secondary School) in Bayelsa State. It includes non-indigenes and indigenes studying in all the public tertiary and secondary

schools in Bayelsa State. Therefore, the total population for this study was about 5000 (Bayelsa State, Ministry of Education Record, 2019). Source from the Bayelsa State, Ministry of Education Record, revealed the population of the selected public tertiary and secondary schools in Bayelsa State, such as Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island (1500), Federal University,

Sample size/Power calculation and Sampling Procedure

The sample size was determined by the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) formula, which

Give 357. Since the population is a heterogeneous type, the institutional sample

The size of the study was determined using Bowley's proportionate allocation formula.

According to Bowley(1926), after determining the sample size from either of the

Methods: There is a need to distribute the sample size among the various organizations

(respondents) under investigation. The distribution was done as follows.

$$n_1 = \frac{n(N_1)}{N}$$

where;

n_1 = Unit sample size for each institution

N_1 = Population sample size for each institution

N = Total sample size for all institutions

N = Total population size.

The details of the distribution are computed as follows:

$$N \text{ (Population Size)} = 5000$$

$$N \text{ (sample size)} = 357$$

$$N_1 \text{ (Niger Delta University)} = 1500$$

To compute the n_1

The number of unit sample sizes distributed for the Niger Delta University we have

$$n_1 = \frac{357 \times (1500)}{5000}$$

$$n_1 = 107$$

The unit sample size for each institution (n_1) was determined using their respective population size for each institution (N_1).

Sampling Technique

This study adopted both stratified and convenience sampling techniques.

Instrument for Data Collection

The research instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument was developed based on a review of related literature. The questionnaire was titled "Sexual Disposition and HIV-risk Factors among Tertiary and Secondary School students in Bayelsa State (SDHRFATSSB)". It comprised two sections. Section A, which consists of demographic data of the respondents, such as the name of the school, sex, age, class, and preliminary questions. Section B contains questions aimed at answering the research questions raised for the study.

Pre-test says piloting of the questionnaire

Pre-test investigation was conducted in two tertiary institutions and Secondary Schools outside the Schools under investigation in the state. The questionnaire was distributed and retrieved, and internal consistency was determined by the Cronbach's Alpha Score. Chronbach's Alpha Score of 0.738 was obtained after the pretest.

Method for Data Analysis

Regression analysis was used for the instrument with the aid of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. Pearson chi-square tests and t-tests were also used to reveal lines of relationship between variables and the specific institutions of the study.

Ethical consideration

Consent was obtained from the institution of study and the participants before the administration of the questionnaires.

RESULTS

Demographic data

The respondents from the four institutions of the study recorded the participation of more female students (206; 58.4%) within the age brackets of 20-29 (142; 40.2%). A good number of the respondents were living off campus (248; 70.3%). They were more of the Southern part of the country (219; 62%) and of Christian background (338; 95.8%). Almost all the respondents are single (336; 95.2%).

Table 1: Demographic Data of Respondents Re-work the tables

Variables	Response	No.
Age	Below 20	126
	20-29	142
	Above 30	61
Sex	Male	147
	Female	206
Residence	Off campus	248
	Campus	105
Institution	NDU	106
	FUO	106
	Belary	56
	Otuasega	85
Ethnicity	South	219
	East	43
	North	63
	West	28
Religion	Christianity	338
	Islam	15
	Traditional	0
Marital status	Married	16
	Single	336
	Divorced	1

Social activities & practices

The dichotomized response pattern of this section shows that there is a high rate of involvement of students of secondary and higher education in high-risk social activities that are risk factors of HIV and related diseases. These observations, though generally found not to be significant, showed that the self-reported odds of contracting HIV were high.

Table 2: Sexually explicit social activities & practices amongst respondents. Can you do inferential stats here?

Variables	Engagement	Non-Engagement	Sig.
Sexual Intercourse	26.3	60.1	.175
Smoke marijuana or alcohol before having sex?	193.0	73.1	.180
Take Lizard dumb, or inhale Paints or Cola nuts before having sex?	86.0	253.0	.791
Take substances like lizard dumb, paints, kolanut, coffee, Tramadol, and activities?	139.0	156.1	.155
Engage in bisexual among yourselves?	152.0	157.5	.009
Surf the internet for sexual films?	274.0	50.4	.229
Pressurized for sex chatting with friends on social media?	263.0	60.3	.245
Engage in social and emotional activities involving sex per week while you are in school?	252.0	53.3	.720
Engage in Oral sex among friends?	248.0	66.9	.230
Engage in Anal sex?	266.0	73.9	.035
Go for night parties, clubs etc?	266.0	66.3	.982

Abbreviations: Freq. – Frequency; Sig. - Significance

DISCUSSION

The results revealed that the majority of students indulge in sexual intercourse (74.5%) and smoking marijuana and drinking alcohol before having sex (54.7%). Other reported high-risk behaviours include surfing the internet for sexual films (77.6%) and being pressured for sex (74.5%). In a study carried out by Okonkwo *et. al.* (2025) among undergraduate students of a tertiary institution in Delta State, Nigeria, reported that 48% of respondents use strong drugs for sex, 62.1% reported that they watch pornographic films, while 46.0% reported inconsistent or no condom use during sexual activity.

Indulgence in risky sexual behaviors is associated with certain risks, including contracting sexually transmitted infections (STIs), such as HIV/AIDS, Gonorrhoea, Hepatitis B, Human Papillomavirus (HPV), and also predisposes one to negative health outcomes such as cervical cancer, infertility, and ectopic pregnancy. Risky sexual behaviours can also increase the likelihood of unwanted pregnancies, which could lead to unsafe abortions and further complications. The use of substances before or during sexual activities could impair judgment and thus increase these risks (Pepple *et. al.*, 2023)

Pearson chi-square and t-tests performed between the age

and gender difference of the several institutions revealed that there is a significant level of sexual activities carried out mostly by average-aged female students in FUIO (age $p=0.0091$) and BELARY (age $p=0.0222$) compared to their counterparts in the study. Taking of Lizard dumb, or inhaling Paints or Cola nuts before having sex was found to be the activities of students in NDU ($p=0.0035$) and FUIO ($p=0.0260$). On toeing the lines of institution-based risk behaviour, students in NDU were found to be more predisposed to being pressurized for sex chatting with friends on social media ($p=0.0354$), engaging in social and emotional activities involving sex per week ($p=0.0088$), and engaging in oral sex among friends ($p=0.0006$). FUIO students, in addition, were also found to be more involved in engaging in social and emotional activities involving sex per week ($p=0.0102$) and bisexual activities ($p=0.0363$). Surfing the internet for sexual film ($p=0.0409$), and engagement in social and emotional activities involving sex per week ($p=0.0000$) were more common activities with BILARY

SUMMARY

The majority of respondents of the study were single (336; 95.2%) female students (206; 58.4%) within the age brackets of 20-29 (142; 40.2%). Involvement of respondents in social activities, though generally found not to be significant, but on individual level have high odds of contracting HIV. It was

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that female students within the 20-29 age bracket in two secondary and two tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State reported a high level of sexual disposition with established high odds for contracting HIV at the institutional and individual levels.

Recommendation

The researchers hereby recommend that responsible agencies should concert effort to persuade against the rising form of high-risk sexual behaviour in educational institutions and the larger community. Unending education and campaigning are the watchword.

Limitations of the study

Like most research, limitations were the funds. The time frame for the completion of the research was a major limiting factor.

Students from OTUASEGA were not found to have a specific, pronounced sexual risk behaviour in the study.

The work of Beston, Tapiwa, and Kennedy (2018) reported risky sexual behaviour among students in tertiary and secondary schools, with a corresponding positive association with use of condoms in sexual intercourse with non-marital, non-cohabiting partners. The authors asserted that this is grounded on the positive role that education plays in enlightening society on issues of behavioural change. The 2009 Bayelsa State ERPS report, among others, also included high rates of multiple sex partners, high rates of young women having sex with older partners, and low rates of condom use as recorded factors (Bayelsa State ERPS report 2009). Other scholars have also reported similar findings in other climes (Leigh and Stall, 1993; Abel & Plumridge, 2004; Ritchwood *et al.*, 2015). Bisexuality (Hader *et al.*; 2001, Millett *et al.*, 2005) and substance use (Ritchwood *et al.*, 2015) are also separately reported

found that students most times indulge in sexual intercourse (263; 74.5%) and smoking marijuana and alcohol before having sex (193; 54.7). Risky habits of low engagement reported here were the practice of taking Lizard dumb, or inhaling Paints or Cola nuts before having sex (253; 75.6%), and engaging in bisexual behavior among one selves (157; 56.9%).

However, with the constraints, all attempts were made to undertake a valid, comprehensive study.

Public Health Implication

Contribution to Knowledge

This study found that more female students within the 20-29 age bracket in educational institutions in Bayelsa State have a high level of sexual disposition and a great extent of indulgence in sexual attitudes and perceptions of high-risk practices, with established high odds for contracting HIV.

REFERENCES

1. Abel GE, Plumridge W. Network norms or styles of drunken comportment. *Health Educ Res.* 2004; 19: 492-500.
2. Boies SC, Sheana B, McFarlane M. University students' uses of and reactions to online sexual information and entertainment: Links to online and offline sexual behaviour. *Can J Hum Sex.* 2002; 11: 77-89.
3. Hader SL, Smith DK, Moore JS, et al. HIV infection in women in the United States: Status at the millennium. *JAMA.* 2001; 285: 1186-1192.
4. Leigh BC, Stall R. Substance use and risky sexual behaviour for exposure to HIV: Issues in methodology, interpretation, and prevention. *Am Psychol.* 1993; 2: 56-73.
5. Millett GA, Peterson JL, Flores SA, et al. Comparisons of disparities and risks of HIV infection in black and other men who have sex with men in Canada, UK, and USA: A meta-analysis. *Lancet.* 2012; 380: 341-348.
6. Okonkwo B, Aduloju RA, Ogbolu CN, et al. Risky sexual behaviours: Predictors and perceived effect on the health of undergraduate students in a tertiary institution in Delta State, Nigeria. *J Interv Epidemiol Public Health.* 2025; 8: 3.
7. Pepple BG, Isabu AC, Muojekwu EE. Risky sexual behavior practices and its associated factors among married women in Obio/Akpor local government area of Rivers State, Nigeria. *World J Adv Res Rev.* 2023; 17: 345-355.
8. Bayelsa State Ministry of Health. Report of the state-wide rapid health facility assessment in preparation for elimination of mother-to-child transmission of HIV. 2013.
9. Ritchwood HF, Tiarney D, Jamie D, et al. Risky sexual behaviour and substance use among adolescents: A meta-analysis. 2015; PMID: PMC4375751.
10. Travasso SM, Mahapatra B, Saggurti N, et al. Risk of HIV transmission through condomless sex in serodifferent gay couples with the HIV-positive partner taking suppressive antiretroviral therapy (PARTNER): Final results of a multicentre prospective observational study. *Lancet.* 2019; 393: 2428-2438.
11. Shaughnessy K, Byers ES, Walsh L. Online sexual activity experience of heterosexual students: Gender similarities and differences. *Arch Sex Behav.* 2011; 40: 419-427.
12. Weiss RA. How does HIV cause AIDS. *Science.* 1993; 260: 1273-1279.

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